

THEORETICAL AND METHODOLOGICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF MERCHANDISING ACTIVITIES IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES

Shomuradova Sh.Sh.

Assistant of the department of Organization of pharmaceutical work of SamSMU

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Abstract. *Today, increased competition in the "producer-consumer" network and competition between retailers forces market participants to focus on ensuring a competitive advantage for their stores. Merchandising (translated from English - the art of selling) is a marketing direction that helps to promote retail sales, drawing the attention of potential buyers to certain goods or groups of goods at the point of sale.*

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Today, increased competition in the "manufacturer-consumer" chain and competition among retailers are forcing market participants to focus on ensuring competitive advantage for their stores. In order for retail enterprises to be distinguished by their individuality and attract buyers, it is necessary not only to skillfully use all the traditional levers of influence on the buyer, but also to look for new ones. The success of leading retailers in the competition is due to the introduction of Merchandising Technologies.

At present, radical changes in the economy of Uzbekistan, industrial diversification, new approaches in the service sector, including in trade activities, necessitate the use of innovative technologies from retail enterprises operating in the market. Based on this, most retail enterprises operating in Uzbekistan are working using the merchandising technique, which is one of the innovative marketing technologies.

Merchandising (translation from English - the art of trade) is a marketing direction that helps to stimulate retail trade, attracting the attention of potential buyers to certain groups of goods or goods at the point of sale. Today, the task is to ensure that the product is buyer-proof, that the consumer has the necessary characteristics. After the creation of the brand of one brand, Muayan is determined by its optimal response to the "price-quality" criterion, packaging and methods of moving the product, and the release of the brand to the market is carried out. Along with the release of goods to the market, attention is paid to the methods and means of sale.

As we know, the consumer is an important and prime element of the market. In addition, the consumer is considered an important factor in the competitive environment. In subsequent years, psychologists have found out that the consumer in most cases buys goods, occurs not on the basis of the previously established landmark, but on the basis of a sudden, emergency emerging decision. That is, "came, saw, bought", in the form of which the implementation of the purchase was observed. Let's take an example from life: a person comes to the supermarket with the intention of buying the products he needs for his needs. He goes to the shelf he is looking for, checks it in a few seconds and draws his attention to a product that has attracted him more than others. In addition, he can explore other products on the shelf or continue to search for a specific product. However, in most cases, the consumer chooses the product that he sees first.

According to various studies, consumers who visit retail outlets forget their frequently purchased products after entering a trading enterprise and buy a product that is a substitute product for the product they are looking for “caught their eye”. Various experiments have shown that 80% of decisions related to the choice of a brand are made directly in the trading hall. This work in the system of Marketing Communications is called merchandising, that is, the promotion of brands in the retail network.

Merchandising is a marketing direction that stimulates retail sales by attracting the attention of Final customers to certain groups of goods or goods at points of sale without the active participation of Special employees, and the art of trade is a set of measures aimed at promoting a specific product, brand, packaging, produced directly at a point of sale, on a trading platform.

In recent years, merchandising has become more in demand due to the improvement, expansion and saturation of the market, as well as increased competition. Merchandising is always aimed at a specific result: to stimulate the desire of the final consumer to choose and purchase the advertised product. Its goal is to increase sales through retail chains and attract new customers. Various methods are used in merchandising, which often have a non-verbal effect on the purchase decision.

The concept, essence of merchandising: merchandising is a marketing direction that helps stimulate retail sales by attracting the attention of Final buyers to certain brands or groups of goods in places of sale without the active participation of Special employees. Most buyers rush and sometimes forget to make all the necessary purchases. Sellers cannot help all buyers choose the right product. Merchandising provides the product with ease for both the consumer and the seller. The correct placement of goods and promotional materials will remind the buyer about the company's products and affect the purchase decision. Merchandising-from English “retail art” is translated as retail Policy, Promotion and sale of certain goods in its own store. From the point of view of the profession, merchandising is a type of independent activity that is professionally carried out on the management of the behavior of buyers based on the analysis of the distribution of the cognitive resources of the individual. Merchandising is a set of measures to promote goods through final consumer points. Merchandising is one of the elements of the strategy for the development of the trading network and a reliable way to generate additional income for retail enterprises. Merchandising is an effective technology for managing calculations and placing products, which makes it possible to significantly increase sales of products in retail outlets. Merchandising is the “language of communication”between the store and the buyer.

The correct use of trading tools is to reduce the cost of informing consumers within the point of sale. A merchandising tool is understood as a means of influencing a merchandising object, while a set of tools is a set of tools and methods to achieve the goals of merchandising.

There are a number of approaches to the definition of Merchandising in general. Of particular importance are the approaches of Russian specialist scientists. Table 1.1 below lists the definitions given to merchandising.

Summarizing the approaches to the activity of merchandising above, we can note the main thing: merchandising is part of marketing, which is any activity aimed at ensuring effective promotion of goods at the retail level. The main requirements for the use of merchandising:

- the enterprise should always have a full range of goods;
- a special design is necessary: the organization of trading halls, including special cooling devices, racks, showcases, counters, etc;
- placement of equipment in the Hall, painting of walls, lighting;

within the enterprise, small retail outlets, as a rule, should be created with more expensive and exclusive goods;

the display of goods should be carried out in such a way as to "force" the consumer to walk through the trading halls of the enterprise for as long as possible, almost without resorting to the help of sellers.

Merchandising is one of the modern tools of marketing communications that use methods of psychological impact on the consumer;

Merchandising is an independent type of activity that is professionally carried out in customer behavior management, based on the analysis of the distribution of human cognitive resources.

Setting goals is the starting point for determining the scale and types of work (functions) that ensure their achievement. Functions of the same type, which are often repeated, can be represented as merchandising tasks.

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